

Constructing a True 3-D Model of a Karst Cave Using an UAV

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Abstract—Karst caves constitute an essential element of natural landforms. Construction of an accurate 3-D model of karst caves is crucial to guide geological exploration, underground space development, and safety in building construction and operation. Karst caves' subterranean location and various challenges such as weak lighting, attenuated satellite positioning signals, texture degradation, and unstructured surface scenes make true 3-D modeling of underground spaces challenging. Current methods of true 3-D modeling rely mostly on expensive and complex lidar scanning combined with ground mobile platforms or supplemented light source photography and multi-view stereo reconstruction. However, these methods are costly for karst cave reconstruction. Our proposed method for reconstructing the true 3-D model of the cave relies on the adaptability of a depth camera to low light environments. It is based on the data captured by an onboard depth camera of a drone for visual autonomous positioning and the surface reconstruction of unstructured scenes. We reconstructed the true 3-D model of Xuansu Cave located in Chibi City, Hubei Province, China. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed method has the potential to reconstruct the true 3-D model of the underground karst cave surface efficiently and with stability. Furthermore, the use of light and small drones equipped with depth cameras presents a low-cost solution. These drones provide fast and reliable exploration of underground caves and offer true 3-D model reconstruction capabilities.

I. INTRODUCTION

Karst caves are underground spaces formed through the process of karstification in soluble rocks and can differ in scale. The cave can have varying shapes, with some parts resembling squares and others resembling narrow promenades. Karst caves exhibit unique and intricate shapes and contain a complex structure of various features such as stalagmites, stone pillars, and stalactites. The complex composition of these natural features creates peculiar landscapes, as demonstrated in Figure 1. Karst caves are abundant

in resources that include water, minerals, tourist attractions, historical and cultural significance, and more. Consequently, conducting an investigation and implementing management practices in underground spaces such as karst caves is vital in enhancing the 3-D monitoring and preservation of natural resources.

Figure 1 Xuansu Cave, located in Chibi City, Hubei Province, China

The traditional digital terrain model (DTM) uses pictures with 3-D effects to map on a flat 2-D base map to create a 3-D visual representation. It is a fundamentally 2-D model, sometimes referred to as a "2.5-D model". The "2.5-D" model only contains prefabricated textures with 3-D effects, making it viewable from only a fixed angle and limiting its ability to meet the observation needs of differing directions and heights of terrain and landforms. Additionally, the analysis function is identical to that of the 2-D

model. Another "2.5-D" model renders elevation data from 2-D data to achieve a visual 3-D representation. While a certain level of 3-D analysis can be achieved through elevation data, the reconstruction method is not sophisticated enough to provide a detailed description of natural landforms such as caves with complex structures. A true 3-D model is the most intuitive representation of the real world. It is a digital space that reflects and expresses the ecological space in a certain range in a real, 3-D and time-series manner. It is a standardized product of new basic surveying and mapping and an essential new infrastructure that provides a unified spatial base for economic, social development, and informatization. Consequently, the development of a true 3-D model of the interior surface of a scene like a cave has become one of the most direct and efficient methods for the investigation and monitoring of underground space resources. Generally, the true 3-D model of underground space can be constructed by various methods, including airborne laser scanning (Airborne Laser Scanner, ALS) [1–3], terrestrial laser scanning (Terrestrial Laser Scanner, TLS) [1,2], Restoring Structure-Motion from Multi View Stereo (SfM-MVS) [4,5], and Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) technology. The scanning method typically depends on costly and bulky lidar equipment that requires a high load capacity for the mounting platform, and the material within the cave may cause the laser scanning to deteriorate. However, the SfM-MVS approach necessitates uniform lighting conditions in dark caves, necessitating the use of professional photographic lighting equipment, which can be challenging to acquire in large caves.

We have devised a method for constructing an accurate 3-D model of a cave using depth camera SLAM. We utilize a small quadrotor UAV as a mobile platform to conduct experiments in a cave situated in Chibi City, Hubei Province, China, as depicted in Figure 2. We provide a detailed description of the specific and experimental processes involved in the method, along with the analysis, below.

Figure 2 The UAV scanning the karst cave

II. METHODOLOGY

To mitigate the effects of lighting factors, we utilize only the depth image data obtained from the airborne depth camera to construct a 3-D model of the cave surface. Using a Truncated Signed Distance Field (TSDF) algorithm and a continuous input of depth image frame sequences, 3-D points with sensor uncertainty are fused to create a dense 3-D point cloud model. If a model point \bar{P}_l reappears in the point cloud fusion process and is observed by the depth image I_d again, we re-calculate its vertex coordinates $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_l$ and normal $\bar{\mathbf{n}}_l$, as indicated by

$$\bar{\mathbf{v}}_l = \frac{\bar{c}_l \bar{\mathbf{v}}_l + \alpha \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{u})}{\bar{c}_l + \alpha}, \text{ and } \bar{\mathbf{n}}_l = \frac{\bar{c}_l \bar{\mathbf{n}}_l + \alpha \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{u})}{\bar{c}_l + \alpha},$$

where \bar{c}_l represents the weighted number of times the model point is observed, and $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{u})$ and $\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{u})$ are the 3-D points and their normal projected from pixel \mathbf{u} in the depth image I_d to the world coordinate system, respectively. Different from the traditional point cloud fusion method [6], we introduce a confidence factor α , so that the number of observed model points \bar{c}_l is weighted average as

$$\bar{c}_l = \bar{c}_{l_{pre}} + \alpha.$$

This is based on the assumption that the normalized radial distance γ of the depth camera measurement error from the center of photograph is Gaussian distributed, so α is expressed as

$$\alpha = e^{-\gamma^2/2\sigma^2},$$

where $\sigma = 0.6$ is the experience value.

Our point cloud fusion modeling method provides robust denoising results, especially for depth cameras at the consumer level with significant sensor uncertainty. Finally, to obtain the surface of the reconstructed scene, we use ray casting and trilinear interpolation to extract the zero-crossing surfaces that are implicitly stored in the TSDF voxel grid.

The usage of regular voxels to store TSDF data to manage and reconstruct the surface of the scene has the potential to be sparse [7]. However, this sparsity significantly wastes memory resources, increases the computational burden of the algorithm, and negatively affects system performance. To address these issues, we use a simple hashing scheme to compactly store, access, and update the implicit surface in our work. This approach enables us to achieve scalable true 3-D reconstruction in large-volume caves and significantly conserves the limited computing and storage resources. Unlike the practice of pre-setting the reconstruction range of rules [6,8], which is not feasible for unstructured underground caves due to their unknown and ever-changing geometry, our approach is more suitable for this type of environment. Additionally, to accommodate large-scale reconstructions, we employ a bidirectional CPU-GPU data flow scheme [7]. This is achieved by creating an active area, containing the reconstructed surface and a secure zone around the current depth camera perspective, which moves with the camera. To

ensure efficient use of resources, when the camera moves beyond a certain distance from the current position, the voxel block data that was initially in the active region is streamed from the GPU and may either be saved to the CPU or to a disk. If the camera returns to the previously reconstructed area, the voxel block data for that region is then streamed from the CPU to the GPU in the same way. This combination of dataflow schema and hashing schema is ideal for the reconstruction of unstructured scenes, as it does not necessitate the reorganization of the hash table for input or output voxel blocks.

Obtaining accurate image poses is crucial before utilizing depth images for surface reconstruction. However, on UAV platforms, traditional pose estimation methods often fail due to the camera's fast movement, which leads to incorrect pose estimation results. To address this issue, we estimate the pose of the airborne depth camera in real-time, using the method of particle swarm template stochastic optimization [8]. However, in contrast to the existing literature [8], we adopt a sparse scene expression in our approach, wherein the number of particles participating in fitness calculations is limited by the active area constructed. Specifically, only the most effective pixels of the current frame can be projected to the sparse scene in the particle swarm template. The particles that correspond to the surface of the scene and are located in the active region calculate their surface fitness and are processed in parallel on the GPU. The aim of this approach is to estimate the fast-moving camera's pose while also conserving the onboard computer's limited computing and storage resources, thereby expanding the UAV's operating range to a larger area. Our experiments demonstrate a remarkable enhancement in the efficiency of our position estimation method compared to the existing literature [8].

III. PRELIMINARY RESULT

Our mobile platform is the AMOV P450 UAV, which has a wheelbase of 450mm and a 1kg payload capacity. It comes equipped with an Intel RealSense D435i depth camera with an effective measurement distance of 8m. All of our experiments were conducted on the Nvidia Xavier NX embedded computing device, which boasts a six-core ARM Cortex-A57 CPU and a dual-core NVIDIA Denver 2.0 CPU that provide processing capabilities of 1.3 TFLOPS. The device is further equipped with 8GB of LPDDR4x RAM, along with a NVIDIA Volta GPU with 512 CUDA cores, and 16GB of high-speed HBM2 memory, enabling quick and efficient data transfer and processing. Our experiments were conducted in Xuansu Cave, an underground cave located in Chibi City, Hubei Province, China.

Figure 3 (a) and (b) represent the data acquired by the airborne depth camera, there is motion blur in (a), and (c) represents the real 3-D model reconstructed from its perspective.

Equipped with a depth camera and an onboard computer, the UAV scans the cave's interior. Our use of the path planning algorithm [9] results in a fully autonomous UAV reconstruction task process that requires no manual intervention. The path planning algorithm, proposed SLAM algorithm, and two-way communication channel between the UAV and the ground are all facilitated via the Robot Operating System mechanism on the airborne computer. Our experiments prove the effectiveness of the depth-only positioning method [8] due to the insignificant effect of motion blur on the depth image, as opposed to the color image, which could be affected. This observation is shown in Figure 3. The intel Nvidia Jetson Xavier NX computer processes the 320x240 depth images in real-time for UAV positioning, attitude determination, and scene reconstruction with a processing rate of 40 frames per second, significantly faster than the rate stated in the literature [8]. This speed is due to our method's beneficial usage of scene sparsity and active area constraints to accelerate stochastic optimization of particle swarm templates. Lighting fixtures were installed in the cave to enhance the reconstructed 3-D model's display, allowing for the color of the point cloud to be captured and utilized in rendering a true 3-D model in color. We present a tunnel of the reconstructed 3-D model in Figure 4. Figure 4 illustrates our method's ability to reconstruct the tunnel's basic geometric shape, with clear geometric texturing of the tunnel walls. Our approach largely reconstructs the scene's inherent geometric structure. Our positioning method relies solely on the depth image acquired by the depth camera for autonomous UAV positioning. While the color image obtained by the depth camera is used only for rendering purposes, our method does not depend on color textures.

Figure 4 The true 3-D model of Xuansu Cave reconstructed using our method.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Despite challenges such as attenuated satellite positioning signals, weak lighting, texture degradation, and unstructured surface scenes, our use of a depth camera enables the UAV's autonomy in obtaining geometric information of the underground natural landforms. This results in successful high-precision real-time scene reconstruction and positioning.

Unfortunately, due to the limited measurement distance of current consumer level depth cameras, resulting in a considerable number of invalid depth values in depth images obtained in too open scenes, which severely impedes the application of autonomous reconstruction in large scenes. Besides enhancing the depth camera to increase its measurement range, constructing a path planning method for drones to scan close to the surface of the scene is a direction deserving researchers' attention.

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